

PEDAGOGICAL AND PRAGMATIC FACTORS OF THE INTERESTS OF THE YOUTH OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

Djumagulova Anora Normakhmatovna

Nursing Academy “Socio-Economic Sciences in Medicine” teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15332114>

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada yoshlar bilan ishlash bo'yicha mutlaqo yangi tizim yaratilayotgani, yoshlarda mamlakat va xalq taqdiriga daxldorlik hissi kuchayib borayotgani, Yangi O'zbekistonni barpo etishda yosh avlodning munosib ishtirok etayotgani ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Yangi O'zbekiston, Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati, yoshlar ma'naviyati, yoshlar manfaatlari, yoshlar bandligini ta'minlash, beshta muhim tashabbus, “Yoshlar daftari”.*

Аннотация. *В статье показано, что создается совершенно новая система работы с молодежью, у молодежи растет чувство сопричастности к судьбе страны и народа, молодое поколение принимает достойное участие в построении Нового Узбекистана.*

Ключевые слова: *Новый Узбекистан, Государственная молодежная политика, духовность молодежи, интересы молодежи, обеспечение занятости молодежи, пять важных инициатив, “Молодежная тетрадь”.*

Annotation. *The article highlights the creation of a completely new system for working with youth, the growing sense of belonging among young people to the fate of the country and the people, and the worthy participation of the younger generation in building a New Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *New Uzbekistan, State Youth Policy, Youth Spirituality, Youth Interests, Ensuring Youth Employment, Five Important Initiatives, “Youth Notebook”.*

A New Uzbekistan is being built, which will embody the eternal dreams of our people and occupy its rightful place in the world community. Efforts towards this dream require a systematic approach to youth issues alongside socio-economic, cultural, spiritual, and political-democratic advancement. The rapid development of New Uzbekistan, its place in the world community in the fields of economy, education, IT, medicine, science, and others, as well as its ability to compete in the international arena, depends on the potential of young people, who make up 60 percent of the country's population. In this regard, it is necessary to improve state youth policy and take into account the requirements of modern development.

First of all, it is necessary to educate and provide social protection to young people, to form them competitive in science, professions, creative thinking, and activity. ...»To achieve significant results, turning youthful enthusiasm, zeal, and courage, noble aspirations into practical actions, a person must live with a clear goal in mind»[1]. Today, the activity of young people is more important than ever, as they are the main driving force of society's development. Therefore, youth should be an inexhaustible source of innovations, ideas, and solutions. In the New Uzbekistan, ensuring the legal rights and interests of young people, realizing their dreams, aspirations, abilities, and potential has become the most important and priority direction of state policy, and reforms in this direction are being carried out in stages. In particular, over the past seven years, more than 100 laws, decrees, and resolutions directly related to the lives of young people have been adopted.

The fundamental reforms being implemented in our country in the field of youth policy, as in all spheres, and the amendments being made to legislation, have shown the need to improve this law based on modern requirements. Therefore, the State Youth Policy was revised, and on September 14, 2016, amendments and additions were made to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On State Youth Policy», which was adopted anew.

The Law provides for: ensuring the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of youth; protecting the life and health of young people; promoting the spiritual, intellectual, physical, and moral development of young people; ensuring open and quality education for young people; creating conditions for the employment of young people and their employment... [2] and a number of other youth-oriented areas. In the implementation of state youth policy, the work carried out within the framework of the five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to enhance the spirituality of youth and organize their meaningful leisure time has been quite effective. The five initiatives cover such important areas as culture, art, sports, the study and use of computer technologies, the development of reading among young people, and the employment of women. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly (September 19, 2017), emphasized that «our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to realize their potential, to prevent the spread of the «virus» of the idea of violence», and proposed to develop an international UN Convention on the Rights of Youth [3]. Based on this proposal, reforms in our country have deepened and become interconnected. Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 23 of January 18, 2021, «On Approving the Concept for the Development of State Youth Policy in Uzbekistan until 2025» [4].

The Concept is implemented annually based on a strictly defined and approved “roadmap” of work. The mechanism of state youth policy in our country and its practical results have been the focus of attention of the world community. Therefore, in 2018, Uzbekistan became a member of the Youth Council of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, and in 2020, the Council for Youth Affairs of the CIS Member States. At the initiative of the President of our country, the «Central Asian Youth Forum,» the 15th meeting of the Youth Council of the SCO member states, the «Best Startup Project among the Youth of the SCO Countries» competition, and the IV Forum of Young Leaders of the Organization of Turkic States were held, and the city of Bukhara was declared the first capital of youth initiatives of the Turkic world, and 2022 was declared the «Year of Supporting Youth Initiatives» in the Turkic world. Also, Shavkat Mirziyoyev's proposal at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council in 2021 to develop and adopt a resolution on the impact of the pandemic on the rights of youth was adopted and put into practice that same year [5]. The delegation of Uzbekistan also took part in the UN Economic and Social Council - «ECOSOS-2023» Youth Forum, which was held at the UN headquarters with the participation of heads of ministries and departments responsible for youth policy from 193 countries.

The State Prize «Mard o'g'lon» and the «Kelajak bunyodkori» (Builder of the Future) medal were established to duly recognize the fruitful work of talented young people with high scientific potential and achieving high results. June 30 was declared «Youth Day». Youth festivals and spiritual-educational events under the motto «Youth of New Uzbekistan, let's unite!» are held annually not only in regional centers, but also in all districts and cities. Within the framework of «Youth Month», «Culture, Art, and Tourism» weeks were organized in mahallas and districts, covering more than 2.4 million young people at various events, projects, public festivals, and gala concerts. In order to increase among future generations the number of followers of such scholars as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mirzo Ulugbek, who made a huge

contribution to the development of world science, and Alisher Navoi, who occupied a special place in the history of the development of the culture of the Turkic peoples with his thoughts and works, competitions «Heirs of Mirzo Ulugbek,» «Followers of Beruni,» «Continuers of Alisher Navoi» are held.

In particular, such tasks have been set as ensuring the employment of graduates throughout the republic; introducing benefits in professions and positions requiring higher education and employing more than 10 thousand young people without higher education; making it mandatory for high school students to study at least one profession and craft in demand in the labor market; allocating land for young people to engage in agriculture. In order to increase the effectiveness of work with young people, the social status, abilities, and interests of young men and women aged 14 to 30 in our country were studied, and they were divided into three categories. Work with young people will be carried out on the basis of a targeted system «from the mahalla to the ministry,» based on specific criteria. At the first stage, 396 thousand young people in the «severe» category, in need of care and attention of the state, were assigned to each minister and his deputy, khokims of regions, districts and cities, heads of sectors, rectors, commanders of the National Guard and military units. 4.6 million young people, who are classified as the second «middle» category and cannot find work in the formal sector, but are economically active, will be helped to solve their problems. Necessary work will also be carried out with 4.4 million young people included in the third «good» category: those who are studying well, have established entrepreneurship, work in the formal sector, are capable, and are socially active.

Today, large-scale reforms aimed at the reliable protection of human rights are being actively implemented in our country. The principle «Uzbekistan - a social state,» enshrined in the Constitution in the new edition, is finding confirmation in our practical life. At the same time, a social state means creating various conveniences for the country's population, in particular, high-quality education, qualified medical care, comprehensive support for families, children, women, the elderly, persons with disabilities, providing housing for people in need of social protection, creating safe working conditions, and solving urgent tasks aimed at reducing poverty. «There is a gap in our spiritual life. Some young people with weak spiritual immunity blindly follow strangers both in behavior and in communication. It would be correct to say that the reason for this is the lack of knowledge and will, not knowing our national identity, our great ancestors,» said President Sh.Mirziyoyev in his book «Strategy of New Uzbekistan,» published in 2021. In this regard, the concept of «New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society» and a national program for its implementation will be developed.

New Uzbekistan is a legal, social, and just secular democratic state, in which the noble idea of «The interests of the people are above all» is confirmed by practical actions, with a strong legislative, executive, and judicial system, and the effective functioning of civil society institutions.

In order to ensure the implementation of the tasks defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On the Strategy «Uzbekistan - 2030,» on the basis of the fundamental reforms being carried out in our country, the unconditional fulfillment of the requirements of the Constitution and laws, the creation of decent conditions for the realization of the potential of every person, the service of man and his happiness, ensuring a peaceful and safe life for every citizen, and caring for the interests of the people are becoming the main criteria of humanism. In this regard, the principle «New Uzbekistan - a social state» is being enshrined as a constitutional norm. In this regard, a number of issues are being resolved in our country, such as

preventing child labor, ensuring reliable protection of the rights of persons with disabilities and representatives of the older generation, providing housing for socially vulnerable categories of the population, establishing the minimum wage, and obtaining a guaranteed volume of medical care for citizens at the expense of the state. The term «rule of law» can be found in many international documents, but it is not given a normative definition. Some consider the rule of law as a scientific doctrine, that is, a product of the scientific views of scientists.

Of course, this is correct. However, there are also those who consider the rule of law a principle. After all, this concept of the rule of law was put forward, studied by scientists, and became a doctrine, and later this concept was reflected in international and national documents and became one of the principles of exercising state power. The first ideas about the rule of law are connected with the views of ancient Greek and medieval thinkers. Despite the adoption of a number of documents in this area, there are no significant changes in solving the problems of youth.

As we strive to build a democratic, legal state, we will never achieve this without protecting the rights of young people, who are our future, without ensuring their active participation in the life of society and the state; thirdly, the state creates conditions for the intellectual, creative, physical, and moral formation and development of young people, for the realization of their rights to education, healthcare, housing, employment, and leisure. For the comprehensive development of young people, it is necessary to create appropriate opportunities for them, that is, to be healthy and have housing, to receive education, employment and recreation. The state undertakes to create appropriate conditions in this regard, since these norms are important not only for the interests of our youth, but also for the prosperous future of our entire society and country.

LITERATURE

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston strategiyasi. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 2021. – 252 b.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni.“Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to‘g‘risida”
<https://lex.uz/docs/-3026246?ONDATE=26.01.2022>
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. BMT bosh assambleyasining 72-sessiyasidagi nutqi. 20.09.2017.
<https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/1063>
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining Qarori. “O‘zbekistonda yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini 2025 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”
<https://lex.uz/docs/-5234746>
5. Prezident Shavkat Mirziyoyevning BMT Inson huquqlari bo‘yicha kengashning 46-sessiyasidagi nutqi. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/prezident-shavkat-mirziyoevning-bmt-inson-huquqlari-boyicha-kengashining-46-sessiyasidagi-nutqi>